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Influence of Demographic Factorson Consumers' Online Buying Behaviour

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Abstract

This paper attempts to explore the effect of demographic factors on consumers' online buying behaviour. The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of demographic factors (age, gender, occupation, marital status, education and income) on online buying behaviour of the consumers. The research approach used in this study is quantitative in nature. Six hypotheses were constructed to investigate the nature of the relationship between the demographic factors and the online buying behaviour. Questionnaires were administered to 100 consumers in kalaburagi city who constituted the sample. Convenience sampling method was used to select the sample. Chi-square-test and descriptive statistics were used to derive results from the data collected with the help of SPSS 20.0. The results revealed that the main influencing demographic factors on online buying were age, occupation, marital status and education level of the consumers. The findings on how demographic factors influence buyingbehaviour can assist online retailers formulate product positioning strategies that create more value for consumer segments thereby enhancing retailer profits. The results of the study could be further used by the researchers and practitioners for conducting future studies in the similar area.

Keywords: *Online buying, Age, Gender, Occupation, Marital status, Education, Income*

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1. Introduction

Consumers today are shopping all the time and everywhere, and in a truly global online marketplace, products can easily be purchased from retailers and manufacturers located anywhere in the world- or from those with no physical retail locations at all. Online spending is taking off. Continued growth in internet penetration and rising e-commerce adoption will drive further growth in the number of online buyers. Multiple factors are behind the rising adoption of e-commerce channels. These include the strong value proposition offered by online merchants, proliferating payment platforms, strengthening delivery logistics, and significant

financial investment in the sector. Thus, retailers need to be exceptionally sensitive and responsive to when and where their potential customers are making purchase decisions (both consciously and subconsciously) throughout their 'always on' shopping journey. Many traditional consumer businesses and new start-ups alike are moving away from models that are shop-centric or geographically-focused, to ones that are customer-centric and virtually borderless (KPMG,2017).According to a report by BCG (2017), in the past three years, the number of online buyers has increased sevenfold to 80 million to 90 million. On the basis of these factors, it is anticipated that the number of online buyers in India will climb to 300 million to 350 million by 2025. In terms of value, online commerce is still a small portion of total retail sales, but it is growing fast. With the increase in online buyers, it is expected that the total value of e-retail will reach 8% to 10% of total sales by 2025. A rising number of consumers in all segments are using the internet as their first port of call in framing and driving their purchase decisions. It is found that about 70% of those who have access to the internet go online to make informed purchase decisions. This number varies among categories of products and services, but it is on the rise everywhere.

Consumers today regularly crisscross online and offline touch points in their purchase journeys, and as a result, multiple types of pathways such as omnichannel interactions are emerging. Almost three-quarters of urban internet users today use only mobile phones to access the internet, compared with 52% in 2014. Falling smartphone prices, less expensive data packages, and the availability of more mobile-friendly content are all driving this growth. The numbers are even higher for young age groups and lower-income segments. As a result, mobile commerce is becoming the dominant force behind e-commerce growth. Eight of ten urban e-commerce transactions take place by phone-across categories, income segments, and regions (BCG report, 2017).

The conventional literature holds sufficient evidence to support the impact of many factors, including gender, education, income, age, households, business and geographical areas at different socio-economic levels (Salomon and Koppelman, 1992) on purchase decisions. However, less empirical evidence is currently available to

support this phenomenon in online buying context and thus, the online consumer behaviour is an emerging research area (Cheung et al., 2005) and the differences across demographic groups has become an interesting research area (Yang and Tung, 2007). There are enough evidences in the literature that socio-demographic factors have impact on individuals' attitudes towards the use of online buying (Cheung et al., 2005; Lightner, 2003; Sim and Koi, 2002; Teo and Lim, 2004). This is also supported by Beneke et al. (2010) who concluded that demographic variables such as income, education and age are likely to have a material effect on purchase intention. This study was, thus, undertaken to investigate the online buying behaviour of consumers with reference to important concerned demographic factors such as age, gender, occupation, marital status, education and income. The results of this empirical study may be useful for online marketing managers for developing effective online strategies for their organisations.

2. The hypotheses

The current research investigates the impact of demographic factors on online buying behaviour of consumers. Six logically bounded hypotheses were formulated. The justification of these hypotheses is given in the following sub-sections.

2.1 Age

Age is among the factors that influence the attitudes of individuals in the use of ICT and different age groups may have different tendencies towards online purchasing (Hwang et al., 2006). This view is also supported by Farag et al. (2003) who reported that age is inversely related to online purchasing in a non-linear manner. Bhatnagar and Ghose (2004) and Beneke et al. (2010) are supporters of the existence of a negative relationship between age and degree of online search. However, there are studies reporting conflicting results. For example, Saarenmaa and Tarja (2005) pointed that 57% of the consumers of e-commerce were 30-years-old or older. This means there is a need for further investigation. Based on this rationale we propose the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between consumers' online buying behaviour and their age.

2.2 Gender

The impact of gender on the use of the Internet and online purchasing has been analysed in various studies and the results have not been found conclusive. For example, Farag et al. (2003) has shown that, in general, most online buyers are male. Similarly, Bhatnagar and Ghose (2004) have found considerable evidence that women display lower levels of computer aptitude and higher levels of computer anxiety. However, Dai (2007) has reported that women outnumber men with respect to both online shopper population and expenditures despite their concerns regarding the risks associated with online purchasing. Jones et al. (2009) found that males are more

intense Internet users than females and have higher purchase intention and attitude to buy online (Rodgers and Harris, 2003). All these may be used as an indication of the fact that some gender differences in the use of ICT should normally be expected. However, the nature of this pattern may change depending on the men's and women's different occupational experiences and their different positions related to professional characteristics in different societies (Losh, 2003). All these may be taken as an evidence of the fact that the attitude of consumers towards online purchasing may depend on their gender and may show differences from the other groups in the society. Therefore, the following hypothesis is postulated:

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship between consumers' online buying behaviour and their gender.

2.3 Occupation

Hashim et al. (2009) stated that individuals in the higher position tend to do more online shopping compared to others in lower positions. This view is also supported by Padmaja and Krishna Mohan (2015) who reported that occupation positively affect online buying behaviour i.e. mostly employees are opting to purchase online. However, there is a study reporting conflicting result. Kothari and Maindargi (2016) reported that occupation of consumers is independent of purchase habit of consumers in online shopping. Thus, there is a need for further analysis and based on this rationale we propose the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relationship between consumers' online buying behaviour and their occupation.

2.4 Marital status

Marital status is an important demographic variable, but there is a difference of opinion among researchers whether it influences online buying or not. Shalini and Malini (2015) mentioned that married respondents of their study preferred online shopping as compared with unmarried respondents. Gong et al. (2013) stated that along with demographic factors like age, income, education, and marital status, the perceived usefulness of these are significant predictors of online shopping. On the contrary, Bhatnagar et al. (2000) found that there is no noteworthy relationship between marital status and online shopping. This view is supported by Richa D. (2012) who stated that marital status precisely does not influence online shopping parameters. However, Singh and Kashyap (2015) found that unmarried people shop more online as compared with married respondents. The reasons advanced for this result are that unmarried respondents have a smaller amount of obligations as rivalled by married people who have to take up the responsibilities of their families. Thus, there is a need for further investigation. Based on this rationale we state the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant relationship between consumers' online buying behaviour and their marital status.

Education level

Palumbo and Herbig (1998) defined the typical Internet user of the twentieth century as being young, professional and affluent with higher levels of education. Sulaiman et al. (2008) found that the younger generation would likely to make online shopping more because of their knowledge in computer technology as opposed to the older generation. Bhatnagar and Ghose (2004) and Tarafdar and Vaidya (2006) also agreed about the impact of education on the Internet and a lack of training and education form significant barriers to the adoption of new technologies. Additionally, most research findings indicate that the better educated use the Information Technology (IT) for diverse tasks and entertainment (Losh, 2003). This backdrop concludes that consumers' education level may be an important factor in understanding their online service usage behaviour. This leads to the development of the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 5: *There is a significant relationship between consumers' online buying behaviour and their education level.*

2.6 Income

Buying online is linked to income and education because such purchases require a computer and internet connection along with the ability to use these. Swinyard and Smith (2003) found that online shoppers are wealthier, better educated, having a high computer literacy, spend more time on computers and the internet, find online shopping easier and entertaining and are not afraid of losses from online transactions. Another body of literature also suggested that education level and higher income bracket may play a significant factor in influencing online shopping behaviour as well (Harn et al., 2006; Haque and Khatibi, 2005; Sulaiman et al., 2008). Goritz et al. (2012) found that buyers with a higher income level buy online more often. Hansen, T. (2005) found that household income positively relates to online shopping. The economic factors which influence online purchasing and payment include income level (e.g. per capita GDP) and availability of credit (e.g. through credit card systems) (Hwang et al., 2006). Data collected by the US National Telecommunications and Information Administration (NTIA) indicates that income correlates with Internet usage (Lightner et al., 2002). Additionally, individuals with a higher income shop online more often (Sim and Koi, 2002). Based on these findings, it will be interesting to investigate the relationship between income and online buying. Against this backdrop, the following hypothesis is formulated:

Hypothesis 6: *There is a significant relationship between consumers' online purchasing behaviour and their income.*

3. Research Methodology

This study uses a systematic analysis to investigate the impact of demographic factors on online buying. A survey approach was used for this purpose and the data were

obtained by means of a questionnaire. Questionnaires were administered to 100 consumers in Kalaburagi city who constituted the sample. Convenience sampling method was used to select the sample. The questionnaire used for the research comprised of questions on demographic variables - age, gender, occupation, marital status, education level, and income. The online buying behaviour was measured using a dichotomous question. Chi-square-test and descriptive statistics were used to derive results from the data collected with the help of SPSS 20.0.

4. Results

Initially, the results of the survey are presented by using descriptive statistics. This is followed by the results of analysis for each selected factor.

4.1 Descriptive results

Descriptive statistics for the sample of customers can be found in table-1, providing information regarding the respondents' demographic profile, such as age, gender, occupation, marital status, educational level and individual income per month. The respondents in the age group of 20-29 years constituted the majority of the sample (65%), followed by 19% of the respondents in the age group of 30-39 years as the majority of consumers shopping online are college students and young working professionals. 62% of the respondents were male and 38% were female.

Table-1: Descriptive statistics for demographics of consumers

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	15-19 years	7	7
	20-29 years	65	65
	30-39 years	19	19
	40-49 years	7	7
	50-59 years	2	2
	60 and above	0	0
	Total	100	100
Gender	Male	62	62
	Female	38	38
	Total	100	100
Occupation	Student	57	57
	Service	9	9
	Professional	15	15
	Business	10	10
	Housewife	9	9
	Total	100	100
Marital Status	Single	66	66
	Married	34	34
	Total	100	100
Education	Intermediate	11	11
	Graduation	39	39
	Post-Graduation	50	50
	Other	0	0
	Total	100	100
Income	Below Rs. 20,000	8	8
	Rs. 20,000- 40,000	16	16
	Rs. 40,000- 60,000	12	12
	Rs. 60,000 and above	2	2
	Dependent on parents' / others' income	62	62
	Total	100	100

Source: Authors' calculation.

The majority of respondents were students, as expected (57%), 15% were professionals, 10% were businessmen, 9% each housewives and service holders. The majority of the respondents (66%) were single and 34% were married. One half (50%) of the respondents were post-graduates and graduates constituted 39% of the sample, who are the young generation generally the college students who are the online shoppers. The majority (62%) of the respondents were dependent on either parents' or others' income, 16% of the respondents' income range was in the range of Rs.20,000- 40,000, 12% of the respondents' income range was Rs.40,000- 60,000, and only 2% of the respondents' income range was Rs.60,000 and above.

4.2 Test results

The chi-square test results for analysing the relationship between various demographic factors and online buying are given in table-2. The examination of p-values in table-2 indicated that there is no sufficient evidence to accept H_2 (Chi-square = 2.333; df = 1; p-value = 0.127). In other words, on the contrary to what is expected, there is no statistically significant relationship between consumers' gender and online buying. This means that there is no disparity in gender in terms of consumers' online buying behaviour. Interestingly, test results were also not in favour of the hypotheses H_6 (Chi-square = 3.860; df = 4; p-value = 0.425) and, therefore, H_6 is rejected. This leads to the fact that the income is not one of the significant predictors of consumers' online buying behaviour. This can also be interpreted as; there is no significant relationship between income and online buying. All the remaining hypotheses were supported by the survey results at 5% significance level and, therefore, H_1 , H_3 , H_4 and H_5 are accepted. In other words, the independent variables age, occupation, marital status and education are significant factors for the explanation of the dependent variable, online buying. This can also be interpreted as; significant disparities exist in the variables of age, occupation, marital status and education in terms of consumers' online buying behaviour.

Table-2. Chi-square results of online buying behaviour with respect to demographics

Dependent variable	Independent variable	Hypothesis value	df	Chi-square	p-value*
Online buying (y)	Age (x1)	H_1	4	17.296	0.002*
	Gender (x2)	H_2	1	2.333	0.127
	Occupation (x3)	H_3	432.211		0.000*
	Marital status (x4)	H_4	2	9.314	0.009*
	Education (x5)	H_5	2	13.775	0.001*
	Income (x6)	H_6	4	3.860	0.425

Source: Authors' calculation.

*Indicates statistically significant at 5% significance level.

5. Discussions

The results suggest that age, occupation, marital status and education level has a significant influence on online buying behaviour. It is inferred that gender and income do not have a significant influence on online buying behaviour.

In this study, test results indicate that consumers' age affects the level of online buying and this effect was found to be negative. In other words, the percentage of the younger group (below 30 years) is higher than the older consumers (above 30 years) for online buying as expected. An interesting explanation of this finding is backed up by Bhatnagar and Ghose (2004), who suggest that as consumers get older, conducting a search requires greater physical effort.

Surprisingly, the results of this study revealed that consumers' gender is not significantly related to online buying. It was observed that male consumers buy online (83.9%) slightly more than their female counterparts (71.1%). This finding is consistent with what was reported by Zhang (2005), who found that there is no statistically significant difference in terms of Internet sub scale usefulness between male and female employees. It can be concluded that gender has no significant association with online shopping. The reason being that the females are now more educated and working in various good positions in the job as like men. Hence, both males and females do prefer online shopping.

It is observed that occupation positively affects online buying behaviour, i.e. mostly professionals and students are opting to purchase online than businessmen and housewives. This finding is in parallel with Padmaja and Krishna Mohan (2015) who reported that occupation positively affect online buying behaviour i.e. mostly employees are opting to purchase online.

The study results suggest that consumers' marital status has a significant impact on online buying. This finding is consistent with the study carried out by Singh and Kashyap (2015) who reported that unmarried people shop more online compared to married. Thus, it can be concluded that, young and single prefer more online shopping than married because they do online shopping for fun and enjoyment.

In this study, it was observed that consumers' level of education has a significant impact on online buying. This finding is in parallel with Farag et al. (2006) and Lightner et al. (2002), who reported that more highly educated respondents buy online more and educational environment has an effect on online behaviour respectively. This means that, as the consumers' education level rises, inclination towards using online purchasing rises.

Prior literature on the influence of income on online purchasing produced consistent results. For instance, Shiu and Dawson (2002) examined the consumer segmentation of the Internet in Britain and Taiwan and found that Internet purchasing is not different among different

income groups. However, Farag et al. (2006) reported that higher income respondents are more likely to buy online and they indicated that economic factors which influence online purchasing include income level. Interestingly, our study indicated that there is no difference in the online buying behaviour among different income groups.

6. Conclusion

The Chi-square test results for consumers' online buying behaviour across different demographic factors show that age, occupation, marital status and education do impact on-line shopping. Based on the research important insights have been gained as to how the selected demographic factors of the consumers affect their online buying behaviour. The results of the study can be utilized by practitioners in relooking or revamping their strategies for online shopping. Online shopping organizations can use the relevant variables and factors, identified from the study, to formulate their strategies and plans. The results can also be used by various organizations to identify their target customer segments as demography is the traditional, easy to apply and perhaps the most important parameter for carrying out market segmentation.

7. Limitations and directions for future research

Although this study has thrown up important learning still it cannot be claimed that it is devoid of any limitations. One major limitation came in the form of using convenience sampling for the purpose of data collection. Probability sampling techniques should form the basis of data collection for future studies. This will help to limit the bias in the sample collected for analysis. It is suggested that larger sample be used in future attempts which may lead to more comprehensive insights into the relationships towards using online buying among consumers. Future studies may consider the role of psychographic variables as a basis for carrying out online shopping market segmentation activities. The combined effect of the different demographic variables on online buying behaviour should be considered as a basis for forthcoming studies. Analysis of individual preferences and group influences on online buying may also provide very interesting results.

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